

Bradley Knobel: It's official, the Ford Bronco Raptor is on the way: will it get to be the best 4x4?

The launch of a Ford Bronco Raptor is official. Bradley Knobel, [Master Certified sales professional at Diffie Ford Lincoln](#), indicates that the wet dream of 4x4 lovers will come true very soon and, following in the footsteps of the entire Raptor saga, Ford Performance will have its own vision of the new Bronco taking its off-road capabilities to the extreme. If the Bronco had already managed to place itself at the top of the category along with the Wrangler, Defender or G-Class, with the arrival of this new version Raptor intends to put land in the middle and become the undisputed king of the category.

Bradley Knobel indicates that the person in charge of confirming this long-awaited launch has been neither more nor less than Jim Farley (CEO of Ford) through his Twitter account, and accompanying the announcement with a first video teaser that marks the launch of the Bronco Raptor for 2022. With this gesture, Ford puts an end to the constant rumors about this version and begins to create the expectation that such a novelty needs, because in just a few weeks it will be presented and therefore orders will be opened.

“More powerful, more radical and better in 4x4 ... the Bronco Raptor aims to become the undisputed king of the off-road,” says [Bradley Knobel](#).

However, very little information is known at the moment about the Bronco Raptor, even so the leaks that have occurred to date make clear several important things. First of all, Bradley Knobel shares that the Bronco Raptor will only be marketed in a 5-door version, something that follows the trend already seen in the Ranger and F-150 Raptor. To this we add the arrival of a more powerful engine, possibly the 3.0 V6 EcoBoost that the Explorer uses to thus exceed 400 hp of maximum power.

Furthermore, according to Bradley Knobel, in addition to the usual aesthetic modifications on these models, the main changes and improvements will focus on the running gear. Here we will find a completely new suspension that will affect arms, shock absorbers, springs, stabilizers, etc. All this will have an impact on higher ground clearance, better off-road dimensions and superior filtering capacity. The all-wheel drive system will also be revised, especially from an electronic point of view, giving weight to the most extreme off-road driving modes and optimizing its operation according to new possibilities.

In short, Bradley Knobel, who [has been working for 30 years in the automotive sector](#), shares that the new Ford Bronco Raptor will take its extreme off-road recipe one step further, being a before and after in its category. A few days after its official launch, what is clear is that Ford is forcing its rivals to make a move if they do not want to lose the throne of the off-road vehicle.